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Nigerians USSD Users Bank Transaction: A Cry Over Foul Play

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ABSTRACT

The conflict over USSD charges has persisted since 2019, with the NCC threatening to disconnect nine banks in January 2024 over unpaid debts. These banks included Fidelity Bank, FCMB, Jaiz Bank, Polaris Bank, Sterling Bank, UBA, Unity Bank, Wema Bank, and Zenith Bank. Daily Trust reports that the number of active bank accounts in Nigeria jumped to 219.6 million in March 2024, which means those using the USSD service run into millions. But daily complaints are common among USSD users across the country even as telecom operators and banks turn a blind eye. The situation becomes more worrisome because neither the banks nor the telecom operators are ready to take the blame, leaving the customers to bear their losses in silence. Frustrated, some of the people who fall victims vowed not to use USSD again. They said telecom operators are ripping them off while nothing is done by the government to address it. The CBN and the NCC should ensure that complaints of customers as related to failed transactions and charges deductions for USSD are resolved in the interest of the customers, financial system and overall economic development. The paper recommends that there's need for a comprehensive public awareness initiative to educate users on how the system works and how to seek redress, because many Nigerians are still in the dark about this unwanted billing charges.

Keywords: USSD, USSD Users, Telecom, Banks, Customers.

INTRODUCTION

Failed bank transactions are not new to many Nigerians as a lot of people have had such experiences, either in form of transfers to other accounts or payment of bills and buying airtime. Failure of transactions is taking a toll on Nigerians, especially business owners, who are now using digital banking for buying and selling (Daily Trust, 2023). The financial sector, particularly the banking industry, has recently experienced significant changes, including remarkable technological disruptions in delivering financial services. Various FinTech companies have emerged, leveraging budding technologies to provide more efficient banking services. As a result, traditional banks have been compelled to adapt these technological innovations to their banking products and services. Consumers have benefitted immensely from this digital paradigm shift, experiencing greater convenience, efficiency, accessibility, and cost savings. However, these innovations also bring numerous challenges that impact the sector. Regulators face the challenge of understanding and regulating financial products and entities that do not fit into conventional categories, while consumers encounter difficulties in resolving disputes arising from failed transactions (Business Day, 2023). The digital banking space faces a significant challenge in carrying out seamless transactions without glitches. The Daily Trust reported that over the past few years, the sector has experienced numerous unresolved failed electronic payment transactions, resulting in substantial financial losses. In the first quarter of 2023, failed payment transactions led to a 4.83% decrease in the value of cashless transactions; from N39.58 trillion recorded at the beginning of the first quarter to N37.67 trillion.

According to the Guardian newspaper, approximately N 49.4 Trillion Naira worth of failed electronic transactions still awaits resolution (Daily Trust, 2025).

These transaction failures commonly occur through unstructured supplementary service data (USSD), failed Automated Teller Machine (ATM) or card transactions, and terminal transactions associated with intermittent slow service and a sluggish internet banking system, among other issues (Business Day, 2023). Customers are raising eyebrows over the indiscriminate and unexplained deductions from their accounts by various banks. The situation becomes more worrisome because neither the banks nor the telecom operators are ready to take the blame, leaving the customers to bear their losses in silence. The bank customers, in separate interviews with the News Agency of Nigeria (NAN) in Abuja on Saturday, complained that attempts to get clarification from their banks were usually met with unsatisfactory responses.

Razak Jubrin, a customer with one of the banks, said that he usually notices unexplained deductions in his savings account whenever he carries out a transaction. “Sometimes, when I recharge my phone through the bank app, I notice certain charges which are not explained. “Sometimes, they debit you and fail to credit your phone with the airtime purchased, and they hardly ever refund your money until you call their customer service desk or even visit the bank to resolve the transaction,” he said (People gazette, 2025).

The (Punch, 2025) reported that since June 18, 2025, when telecom operators started deducting charges for Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) transactions directly from customers’ airtime, bank customers have been complaining about charges on failed transactions via the USSD service. Daily Trust reports that the migration from the previous model where banks deduct the charges to end-user billing follows the Determination of USSD Pricing and Services issued by the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), which was developed in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other key stakeholders. This new model was adopted to put an end to the long impasse between banks and telecommunication companies over USSD debt as the former often failed to remit to the latter after deducting from customers’ accounts. But this has compounded the problem of bank customers using the service (Daily Trust, 2025). Mutmainnah Ajisafe, a primary school teacher in Lagos, had tried to transfer N10,000 to her daughter in the university via a first generation bank’s USSD code, but the transaction failed midway three times, yet N20.94k was deducted from her airtime. She lost N6.98k on each attempt without getting the transaction done. Mutmainnah’s story was one among many cases of bank customers getting failed transactions via the USSD service since June 18. Like Mutmainnah, Ajose Emmanuel, a commercial motorcyclist popularly known as Okada rider, once had issues transferring money via USSD service (Daily Trust, 2023). When Chinyere, a petty trader in Lagos, tried to transfer N5,000 to her supplier using her bank’s USSD code, she thought it would take only seconds. Instead, the transaction failed midway (Nairaland, 2025). Frustrated, she tried again. The second attempt also collapsed without delivering the funds. But when she checked her balance, she discovered N13.96 had been deducted N6.98 for each failed session. Transaction was unsuccessful and she was charged twice without getting any value. Chinyere’s story was not an isolated case. This has been the experience of many bank customers using the USSD channel to perform basic transactions across Nigeria. The situation becomes more worrisome because neither the banks nor the telecom operators are ready to take the blame, leaving the customers to bear their losses in silence (Nairaland 2025).

Who is to Blame Telecommunication Companies or Banks?

Both banks and telecom operators deny blame. Banks argue that once a USSD session is initiated, charges are automatically deducted by telecom operators, whether or not the transaction is successful. Telecoms, on the other hand, say banks’ back-end servers often fail to process transactions in real time, leaving customers stranded. Sources in the banking industry said that telecommunication companies should be held responsible for deductions on failed USSD transactions. But the Chairman of the Association of Licensed Telecommunications Operators of Nigeria (ALTON) Engr. Gbenga Adebayo, said the operators could not be blamed for failed USSD transactions as they deliver their part of the service at every point of a USSD transaction (Daily Trust, 2025). According to him, the telecom operators are like the vehicles

taking the bank customers to their bank, whether they get money from the bank or not is not the fault of the telecommunication companies. “Operators deliver you to the infrastructure of the bank, we have no control over what happens there. “You know, sometimes, just like the ATM where you don’t have money, sometimes when you interact with the bank, the server is resetting, it’s taking signals from somewhere, and you can’t blame the operator for that incomplete service,” Adebayo said in Lagos. Suggesting that the banks should be blamed, epileptic poor network from banks are contributing factor towards failed USSD transaction in the country.

Banks are pointing fingers on telecommunication companies and telecommunication companies are equally pointing fingers on Banks. Meanwhile, a bank official who spoke with Nairametrics on condition of anonymity said the banks could have taken the blame when they were still doing corporate billing, that is, banks deducting charges from customers’ account (Nairaland, 2025) “How can you blame the banks for the money they are not collecting? You know USSD is now on end-user billing, the telecoms are the ones deducting money directly from the customers, not the banks,” he said. Chief Deolu Ogunbanjo said: “USSD is a critical channel leveraged primarily by the financially excluded, vulnerable and critical mass. He also said Nigerian telecom subscribers should sue the banks for failed USSD transactions. The operators and the banks need to go back to the Nigerian Communications Commission and the Central Bank of Nigeria to deliberate on how they will resolve this. The blame will always go to the telecoms industry because they are the ones collecting the money (Nairaland, 2025).

The PUNCH gathered that most commercial banks have not issued advisories to their customers and have not commenced airtime deductions. Sources at some banks admitted to being unaware of the development or undecided on how to proceed. However, Fidelity Bank confirmed it had already notified customers of the change. UBA, in a message to customers, said, “In line with the directive of the NCC, please be informed that effective June 3, 2025, charges for USSD banking services will no longer be deducted from your bank account. Going forward, these charges will be deducted directly from your mobile airtime balance in accordance with the NCC’s End-User Billing model” (Punch 2025)

Hidden Cost Banks Customers Pays

Many Nigerians still depend on USSD for transactions, but the experience of losing money is now discouraging them from using the channel. People are worried who had had to use USSD transaction unsuccessfully, and they will be debited

Quite alright, some people may see the N6.98 as insignificant, multiple deductions of the same amount for unsuccessful transactions has become the hidden costs several bank customers are paying. Because of that reason is making financial inclusion in Nigeria to become more expensive and may discourage many from saving money in their bank accounts. No doubt about it many customers have lost money to transactions as little as checking their BVN or retrieving NIN as they get debited without getting the service satisfaction.

Major Implications of Failed USSD Transaction

“Financial inclusion should not come at the expense of consumer exploitation,” said Lagos-based economist Tunde Bakare. “If rural Nigerians feel cheated, they will return to cash, and that sets us back years” (The Reporters News, 2025)

For Chinedu in Lagos, the decision is already made. “I won’t use USSD again until they fix this. It’s better to queue in the bank than lose my hard-earned airtime.” According to the Reporters News, Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS) data shows that USSD transactions accounted for over ₦8 trillion in value in 2024. If even 1% of those sessions fail while charges are deducted, consumers could be losing more than ₦80 billion annually to failed transactions.

Industry experts estimate that billions of naira could be lost annually if failed transactions continue at the current rate. “We are not just talking about service fees,” said financial analyst Habiba Adamu. “We are talking about people being charged for services that are not rendered. It’s like paying for a bus ticket when the bus never left the station” (The Reporters News, 2025).

Measures in Place to Protect Customers

Under both CBN and NCC regulations, banks and telecom operators are required to notify customers in the event that their banking or USSD services experience downtime. Customers should not be double-billed for the same transaction. To ensure this, the CBN and NCC have put in place several safeguards. These include;

Transparency in Communication:

Banks and telecommunication companies are expected to communicate clearly with consumers regarding the new fee structure, ensuring that users understand they will only be charged once per transaction.

Regulatory Oversight:

The Central Bank of Nigeria and Nigeria Communication Commission are actively overseeing the transition to ensure compliance with these billing rules. Non-compliance by banks or telecom operators could lead to regulatory sanctions, reinforcing the commitment to prevent double billing and protect consumer interests.

Transparency in Clear rules of engagement

NCC has since directed that MNOs must provide you with an end-of-activity notification telling you exactly what you have been charged.

CONCLUSION

The Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Council (FCCPC), which was established to protect consumer interests, would typically intervene to address these consumer issues. However, a law passed by the National Assembly has suspended other regulatory agencies from interfering in the protection of banking and financial services consumers. Specifically, Section 65(1) of the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act excludes the operations of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (FCCPA) in matters affecting the banking sector, particularly concerning acts, financial products, or financial services provided by banks or other financial institutions. One would expect that with the suspension of the FCCPA's provisions, the CBN would provide adequate and speedy mechanisms to assist aggrieved consumers (Business Day, 2023). As digital banking becomes an integral part of the financial sector, regulators must keep pace or closely align with the industry. This will ensure they adequately address emerging issues, particularly in protecting consumer rights. The regulators' responsiveness is crucial in adapting to the changes brought about by digital banking (Business Day, 2023). At stake is not just money, but public trust in digital financial services. For a country pushing financial inclusion as part of its development agenda, experts warn that unchecked exploitation through failed USSD charges could discourage millions from using formal banking channels.

The CBN as financial regulator of the country has come out with the final solution by providing phone number and email to the customers, If you are charged for USSD by your bank, please report immediately to the CBN via phone at +234-70-0225-5226 or email at contactcbn@cbn.gov.ng (The People Gazette, 2025).

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to regain user trust and ensure fairness, the USSD charge must only apply after the transaction is successfully completed. Telecommunication industries must auto-refund airtime where a session fails or terminates prematurely just like bank reversal notifications

Nigeria Communication Commission should compel telecoms to create user-friendly, time-bound dispute resolution platforms where customers can easily report and resolve airtime deductions for failed transactions.

There's need for a comprehensive public awareness initiative to educate users on how the system works and how to seek redress. Because some Nigerians are still in the dark about this unwanted billing charge.

REFERENCES

- Business Day NG (2023). Resolving Failed Transactions in the Digital Banking Sector
<https://businessday.ng>
- Daily Trust, (2025). Billions At Stake As Nigerians Pay For Failed USSD
Transactions.info@dailytrust.com
- Daily Trust,(2023). Amidst Cash Crunch, Nigerians Suffer Massive Failed Unreversed Bank Transaction
- Naira Land (2025). How Nigerians Are Losing Money to Failed Bank Transactions
<https://www.nairaland.com>
- Peoples Gazzete NG (2022). Bank Customers Lament Indiscriminate Charges [https:// gazeettengr.com](https://gazeettengr.com)
- The Punch. (2025). USSD War: Telecoms Oppose Airtime Charges for Bank Transfers
<https://thepunchng.com>.
- The Reporters News, (2025) Nigerians Cry Foul as USSD Users Pay for Failed Bank Transactions
<https://thereportersnews.com.ng>